

23 proteins
(up:9, down:14)

Figure S1. Differentially expressed proteins in the serum between the OFC-positive and OFC-negative groups before OFC

Colored areas in the volcano plot show the differentially expressed proteins upregulated and downregulated in the OFC-positive group relative to the OFC-negative group. Proteome analysis of serum samples was performed using four biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and five biological replicates for the OFC-negative group.